

D1.4 – Data Management Plan

Lead Partner:	EPOS ERIC
Version:	v00
Author(s) (Name, Organisation):	Fulvio Galeazzi (EPOS ERIC), Giovanna Maracchia (INGV / EPOS ERIC)
Status:	Submitted
Dissemination Level:	PU

Deliverable Abstract

This is the EPOS ON Data Management Plan, describing the full lifecycle of data which is generated/reused within the EPOS ON Project.

COPYRIGHT NOTICE

This work by Parties of the EPOS ON Project is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>). The EPOS ON project is funded by the European Union Horizon Europe programme under grant n° 101131592.

QUALITY CONTROL

Date	Name	Organisation
Reviewer 1:	Daniele Bailo	INGV/EPOS
Reviewer 2:	Jan Michalek	UiB

TERMINOLOGY

Acronym	Definition
BED	Built Environment Data
DMP	Data Management Plan
DoA	Description of Action, the description of how the EPOS ON project will be carried out
EPOS Platform	Formerly “EPOS Data Portal”, https://www.epos-eu.org/dataportal
GEM	Global Earthquake Model
ICS-C	Integrated Core Services: the central hub where EPOS users can discover and access data and services provided by TCSs, as well as the distributed resources forming the ICS-D
ICS-D	Integrated Core Services Distributed: the infrastructure providing access to supercomputing facilities and advanced computation, like workflow execution
TCS	Thematic Core Service represent the coordinated provision of data and services within the EPOS Platform, by one of the (currently) 10 EPOS communities
UX	User eXperience
WP	Work Package of the EPOS ON project

Table of Contents

1. Introduction	5
1.1. Context.....	5
1.2. About this document	5
1.3. Document structure.....	5
2. Data Summary	7
2.1. Overview: data products P100, relevant to WP1	19
2.2. Overview: data products P200, relevant to WP2	19
2.3. Overview: data products P300, relevant to WP3	20
2.4. Overview: data products P400, relevant to WP4	20
2.5. Overview: data products P600, relevant to WP6	21
3. FAIR data	22
3.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	22
3.1.1. Findability: data products P100, relevant to WP1.....	22
3.1.2. Findability: data products P200, relevant to WP2.....	22
3.1.3. Findability: data products P300, relevant to WP3.....	22
3.1.4. Findability: data products P400, relevant to WP4.....	23
3.2. Making data accessible	24
3.2.1. Accessibility: data products P100, relevant to WP1.....	24
3.2.2. Accessibility: data products P200, relevant to WP2.....	24
3.2.3. Accessibility: data products P300, relevant to WP3.....	25
3.2.4. Accessibility: data products P400, relevant to WP4.....	25
3.3. Making data interoperable	26
3.3.1. Interoperability: data products P100, relevant to WP1	26
3.3.2. Interoperability: data products P200, relevant to WP2	26
3.3.3. Interoperability: data products P300, relevant to WP3	26
3.4. Increase data re-use	27
3.4.1. Re-usability: data products P100, relevant to WP1	27
3.4.2. Re-usability: data products P200, relevant to WP2	27
3.4.3. Re-usability: data products P300, relevant to WP3	27
3.4.4. Re-usability: data products P400, relevant to WP4	28
4. Other research outputs	29
4.1. Data products P100, relevant to WP1	29
4.2. Data products P200 (WP2), P300 (WP3), P600 (WP6)	29
5. Allocation of resources	31

6. Data security	32
7. Ethics	33
8. Other issues	34

1. Introduction

1.1. Context

The European Plate Observing System (EPOS) is the sole, distributed pan-European Research Infrastructure (RI) for solid Earth Science, enabling open access to high-quality, multidisciplinary data, data products, software and services.

The overall objective of the EPOS ON project is to perform activities aimed at supporting the optimization and evolution of the EPOS Research Infrastructure. Indeed, EPOS ON is seamlessly placed in the EPOS lifecycle, and its first Specific Objective (SO) is “SO1 - Ensuring full exploitation of project results by EPOS ERIC” in order to capitalize on past and ongoing efforts and investments.

EPOS Research Infrastructure promotes Open Science by sharing multidisciplinary solid Earth science data and products to foster research and innovation. Likewise, the EPOS ON project is committed to Open Science by further consolidating the data and service portfolio accessible via the EPOS Platform and by developing prototypes of selected use cases of advanced computing within the user-friendly environment of the Integrated Core Services - Distributed (ICS-D).

1.2. About this document

This Data Management Plan is the document describing the full lifecycle of data which is generated/reused within the EPOS ON Project.

It is a living document, which will be updated at least on a yearly basis, or whenever the need will arise: for example, to include the description of additional datasets, or in case the project decides to update the management procedures for one or more datasets.

The information contained in the following chapters was collected by the WP leaders, who will be responsible for future updates related to their respective activities.

The **data manager** of the EPOS ON project will be Fulvio Galeazzi (EPOS ERIC), who will be responsible for the execution of actions described in this DMP.

While structuring this document, we followed the Horizon Europe DMP template¹, as described in the next section.

1.3. Document structure

Chapter 2 “Data summary” presents a summary of all data products which have been identified by WP leaders at time of writing. Data products are listed in a table, showing some basic information: short name, related WP or Task, whether the data product is reusing data from other sources, data types and formats, expected size, in which context (i.e., by whom) the data may be used/reused.

¹https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/temp-form/report/data-management-plan_he_en.docx

Since the data products share some degree of commonality, to avoid repetitions the following sections of this chapter contain distinct subsections discussing data products grouped according to the relevant WP: a similar approach is followed in the other chapters of this document. Whenever a group of data products needs to be referenced, it will be labeled as “PX00”, i.e. “all data products (P) with three-digit ID starting with ‘X’, associated with work package X of the EPOS ON project”: for example, “P300” refers to all data products produced in the context of WP3.

Chapter 3 “FAIR data” discusses the data products with respect to the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable): the discussion is focused on data products qualifying as “research data”, including metadata.

Other data types are then discussed in **Chapter 4 “Other research outputs”**, presenting an overview of the management of such data products as, for example, project documents and software.

Chapter 5 “Allocation of resources” discusses costs associated with data management and the plan to cover those, during and after the EPOS ON project.

Chapter 6 “Data security” presents the provisions put in place to ensure data security (including availability and recovery) as well as, where needed, long term preservation.

Finally, **Chapter 7 “Ethics”** discusses ethics and legal issues that may have impact on data sharing, while **Chapter 8 “Other Issues”** highlights cases where data management for given data products also need to comply with additional data management procedures defined at national/ funder/ sectorial/ departmental level.

2. Data Summary

The following table lists all “data products” identified by the WorkPackage leaders of the EPOS ON project: the term “data products” encompasses a broad range of data types, like research data, software, publications.

These data products will be used for the successful management of the project, and in order to achieve its objectives, as per the project Description of the Action.

As explained in the Introduction, each group of data products is further discussed in a dedicated section following the table.

Table structure:

- Data Product ID: three-digit code preceded by the letter “P” (for “data Product”). The first digit is the WP number where (most of) such data will be produced or managed, and the following two digits are used to enumerate all data products for such WP
- Tasks involved: Tasks, or whole WorkPackages, dealing with the given data product (read below for WP and Task names)
- Short description: few lines to provide some context on the activity behind the given data product
- Reusing data: is the data product reusing data? If so, a bit of further information is provided about the source of data
- Type: type(s) of data in the given data products
- Data format(s): data format or filename extension or programming language
- Estimated volume: rough estimate of the total amount of data expected at project closure
- Main User/Audience: the main categories to whom data product availability may be relevant:
 - O = EPOS ON project users
 - P = EPOS community and EPOS Platform users
 - R = Researchers
 - D = Developers (e.g., model developers, risk modelers)
 - S = Students
 - M = Decision makers
 - E = Emergency Management Agencies, Civil Protection
 - other categories are mentioned explicitly

For reference, the full names of the EPOS ON work packages and Tasks follow:

- WP1: Project Management, Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication
 - T1.1: Project Management
 - T1.2: Project Governance
 - T1.3: Monitoring and assessment of the project performance (KPIs) and project-related risks (Risk Register)

- T1.4: Dissemination, exploitation and communication
- WP2: Enhancing Services for Science
 - T2.1: Enhanced EPOS catalogue of services for science
 - T2.2: Integration of new communities and stakeholders to the EPOS RI
 - T2.3: Computational Earth Science and tools
- WP3: Contribution to tackle Societal Challenges
 - T3.1: Scientific products to support risk management
 - T3.2: Interaction with operational stakeholders in civil protection and disaster risk management
 - T3.3: Methodology for an ethical label applicable to services
 - T3.4: Environmental analysis of the EPOS service provision
- WP4: Strengthening Impact through User Engagement
 - T4.1: Consolidate and increase the EPOS User Community
 - T4.2: User engagement through communication and training
 - T4.3: Building the user base of early-career researchers
- WP5: Enlarging European and International Collaborations
 - T5.1: Implementation of pan-European collaborations
 - T5.2: Cooperation with international initiatives
 - T5.3: Contribution to EOOSC
- WP6: Optimization and Evolution of the EPOS Research Infrastructure
 - T6.1: Analysis of project outputs in relation to the EPOS Sustainability Plan
 - T6.2: Further engagement of national stakeholders
 - T6.3: Integrated management tools for EPOS ERIC

Data Product	Tasks involved	Short description	Reusing data? Source of data?	Type	Data formats	Estimated volume	Main User / Audience
P101	All WPs and Tasks	Deliverables and publications	N	Standard office documents	PDF, DOCX, PPTX	1 GB	O, P, R, D, other federated infrastructures
P102	All WPs and Tasks	Project Management working documents	N	Standard office documents	PDF, DOCX, PPTX, XLSX	1 GB	O
P103	All WPs and Tasks	Project Management workspace material	N	Structured Text, Standard office documents	Handled internally by the Project Management tool in use (Confluence), DOCX and PDF for exported pages	10 GB	O
P104	T1.4	Dissemination, exploitation, communication material	Y (e.g. material from previous projects or from the RI itself)	Standard office documents	PDF, PPTX, DOCx, Image files (e.g. PNG, JPG, SVG, EPS) Video formats (e.g. MP4)...	10 GB	O, P, R, D, other federated infrastructures

Data Product	Tasks involved	Short description	Reusing data? Source of data?	Type	Data formats	Estimated volume	Main User / Audience
P105	All WPs and Tasks	Lists of contacts , mailing lists, lists of board participants	N	Structured Text	TXT, CSV	100 MB	O, Executive Coordination Office
P201	T2.1, T2.2, T2.3	Metadata for services description in the EPOS Platform	Y: see relevant TCS N for new services	Structured Text	JSON-LD, XML, RDF	<1 MB	O, P
P202	T2.2	Metadata schemas and/or vocabularies for new/extended communities	N / Y	Structured Text	XML, RDF	1-5 MB	O, P
P203	T2.1, T2.3	Software prototypes	N	Structured Text	Software code and documentation (e.g., Python, JS, Fortran, C)	100 MB	O, P

Data Product	Tasks involved	Short description	Reusing data? Source of data?	Type	Data formats	Estimated volume	Main User / Audience
P311	T3.1.1	Alerts by EEW: enhance CREW platform, develop and test EEW approaches and evaluate readiness for operational implementation	N (for development, reuse data from NFO available in EPOS Platform)	Alerts issued in xml format, as standard <i>event.xml</i>	Xml (data), Ttl (metadata)	-	P, E
P321	T3.1.2	Forecast points	N (integrate data from NEAM Member States or TSP)	Geographical locations	GeoJSON	1 MB	NEAM Member States, TSP
P322	T3.1.2	Sea level sensors	Y IOC Sea Level Station Monitoring Facility, available within TSP-IOT in EPOS Platform	Geographical locations, data time-series	Different formats (e.g. ASCII, GeoJSON, JSON,...) upon request via OpenAPI REST standard	500 GB (reused)	TSP, R, D, M

Data Product	Tasks involved	Short description	Reusing data? Source of data?	Type	Data formats	Estimated volume	Main User / Audience
P331	T3.1.3	Global Acoustic Meteotsunami Model: to provide the expected probabilistic meteotsunami hazards for 7 different (potentially super) volcanoes and for 160 cities around the world.	N	Numerical simulations, hazard maps, probabilistic distributions	Not finalized yet. Also depends on the degree of integration within the ICS-D.	10 GB	R, D, M, E
P332	T3.1.3	Adriatic Meteotsunami Surrogate Model: provides probabilistic hazard assessments of maximum sea levels in 3 different locations along the Croatian coastline, up to 24h before any meteotsunami event.	N	Numerical simulation	Matlab interface. Also depends on the degree of integration within the ICS-D.	5 GB	R, D, M, E

Data Product	Tasks involved	Short description	Reusing data? Source of data?	Type	Data formats	Estimated volume	Main User / Audience
P333	T3.1.3	Adriatic Forecast Model: provides daily 1-km resolution atmosphere-ocean 3-day forecasts. Only provided when a meteotsunami occurs.	N	Numerical simulation	NetCDF files. Need for the database to be updated every time an event occurs.	10 GB to 100 TB (scales with number of occurrences)	R, D, M, E
P341	T3.1.4	Improvements to Global Earthquake Impact Database	Y Global Earthquake Impact Database	OpenQuake engine models	NRML files, csv, png (for maps)	1 GB	R, D, M, E

Data Product	Tasks involved	Short description	Reusing data? Source of data?	Type	Data formats	Estimated volume	Main User / Audience
P342	T3.1.4	European exposure models accounting for seasonal variations of population	Y European Exposure Models with seasonal variation, maintained by EFEHR European Seismic Risk Services		csv	5 GB	R, D, M, E
P343	T3.1.4	Database of damage-dependent seismic vulnerability models for European building typologies	Y European building typologies, from Global Earthquake Model database of vulnerability models	OpenQuake models Software simulations	Csv and xml (following NRML standard) Python scripts	100 MB	R, D, M, E

Data Product	Tasks involved	Short description	Reusing data? Source of data?	Type	Data formats	Estimated volume	Main User / Audience
P351	T3.1.5	Embodied Carbon Factors: embodied carbon (kg CO ₂ e) per unit (kg, m ³ , etc.) of a variety of construction materials and building components	Y Environmental Product Declarations, from Scientific papers and online databases (e.g., EC3, Eco Platform, EPD-Hub, Ökobaudat)	Database	Csv, plots Python scripts	10 GB	R, D, M
P352	T3.1.5	Replacement Embodied Carbon: embodied carbon required for the replacement of existing buildings with new constructions (kg CO ₂ e/m ²), which represent a new attribute in European exposure models.	Y European Exposure Models, maintained by Global Earthquake Model (GEM) Foundation	Database Exposure models, including the replacement embodied carbon	Csv, plots, maps Python scripts	10 GB	R, D, M

Data Product	Tasks involved	Short description	Reusing data? Source of data?	Type	Data formats	Estimated volume	Main User / Audience
P353	T3.1.5	Average Annual Embodied Carbon (AAEC) : embodied carbon associated to seismic damage repair and reconstruction activities (kg CO ₂ e/yr) needed in each European exposed asset, as an additional metric of seismic risk	Y Global Risk Model, maintained by Global Earthquake Model (GEM) Foundation	Database	Csv, maps Python scripts	10 GB	R, D, M
P361	T3.1.6	Support services and data products for rapid earthquake infographic	Y (EFEHR, EMSC, ORFEUS, EPOS Platform)	Software product		1 GB	All, including general public
P371	T3.1.7	Online platform providing access to European and Swiss ETAS models (Epidemic Type Aftershock Sequence)	Y	Software product		5 GB	R, S, D

Data Product	Tasks involved	Short description	Reusing data? Source of data?	Type	Data formats	Estimated volume	Main User / Audience
P381	T3.1.8	Prototype service for early ash-/gas dispersion warning	Y (OPGC, IMO and INGV portals, EPOS VOLC-TCS Gateway)	Software product, Software simulations, Database	Python code developments for the Web-GIS interface Vector (e.g. shp) and raster (e.g. GeoTiff) data and products	10 GB	All (O, P, R, D, S, M, E, general public)
P401	T4.2, T4.3	Training materials	Y	Training resources (including slides, audiovisual formats, infographics and supporting documents - e.g resources for trainers and trainees)	.PPTx, .DOCx, .PDF, .XLS, .MD, .TXT and image files	10 GB	All, in particular O, P, R, S

Data Product	Tasks involved	Short description	Reusing data? Source of data?	Type	Data formats	Estimated volume	Main User / Audience
P402	T4.2, T4.3	User feedback	N	User feedback surveys, user interviews transcripts/ recording, UX survey reports	.XLS, .PPTx, .DOCx, .PDF , audio/video formats e.g. MP4		O
P403	T4.2, 4.3	Ready-to-use automated workflows	Y	sample code and related documentation	Jupyter notebooks		P, R, S
P631	T6.3	IT back-office tool and related data	N	Software product, recordings and transcriptions of interviews, financial, administrative, legal data, info on services and service providers	Python, Java, JavaScript, TypeScript		O, P, S, D, other distributed RI

2.1. Overview: data products P100, relevant to WP1

All data products in this category will be generated within the project, with the partial exception of “P104 – Communication material” and “P105 – Lists of contacts” which will also reuse existing material.

Part of the data (“P101 – Deliverables and publications” and “P104 – Communication material”) may be useful outside the project, for example by anyone seeking examples or guidelines to develop or integrate a service into a federated platform.

2.2. Overview: data products P200, relevant to WP2

These data products are connected with WP2 activities, aimed at extending the EPOS Platform with new services and capabilities to access new data. The EPOS Platform itself is not storing any data, hence all these data products are connected to the description, integration and usage of data already existing within the relevant scientific communities: therefore, these data products deal with metadata and software only, while the data management aspects are outside the scope of this DMP. For the same reasons, the scope of the discussion about FAIR aspects has, for these data products, a rather limited scope, as those are just meant to be consumed within the EPOS Platform.

“P201- Services description” refers to the new/updated descriptions of services in the EPOS Platform (following the EPOS-DCAT-AP standard), after the enrichment brought in by EPOS ON WP2 activities. As described in the EPOS ON Description of Activities, the services in question are those related to Task T2.1 subtasks:

1. Multidisciplinary data from Slovenian Karst
2. Innovative geochemical data
3. Data from Geo-Energy Test Beds
4. Enhance Magnetotelluric data and models
5. Muography density imaging
6. World Stress Map
7. Coordinated inventory of mobile instrument pools
8. Harmonized data and associated data services for Vs30, slope, and geology
9. Computation of Rapid solutions in GNSS
10. Airborne survey data

“P202 – Metadata for new/extended communities” refers to the metadata description of additional datasets in view of their integration within the EPOS Platform, and to the improved/harmonized description of datasets already accessible within the Platform. These activities encompass two project Tasks:

- T2.1: for datasets which are already available within the community behind a given EPOS TCS;
- T2.2: for datasets provided by new communities (e.g., Built Environment Data) or new stakeholders (private sector, Krafla Magma Testbed)

“P203 – Software prototypes” refers to software prototypes and tools, developed in the context of T2.1 and T2.3. These latter, in particular, are the first use-cases for the development of ICS-D, enhancing the EPOS Platform by incorporating the workflow execution capacity as well as access to High Performance/Throughput Computing clusters.

2.3. Overview: data products P300, relevant to WP3

Data products in this group are related to WP3 activities, aiming at expanding the EPOS Platform via the enhancement and the integration of services to tackle specific societal challenges related to risk management.

All these data products are specifically connected to Task T3.1, aiming at enhancing and integrating existing services provided by the EPOS Thematic Core Services via the EPOS Platform, to support risk management. As such, they share some common aspects, as will be further discussed in next paragraphs:

- access or reuse of data already available within the EPOS Platform or the TCS,
- adherence to EPOS standards and practices,
- making outcomes available primarily via the EPOS Platform

Details for some services are not yet final. In some cases, like P361 - Rapid earthquake infographic”, the exact form (balance between qualitative and quantitative information content) of the prototype service(s) is still under discussion, at time of writing, also concerning the relevant ethical implications. In other cases, like “P331 – Global Acoustic MeteoTsunami” and “P332 - Adriatic Meteotsunami Surrogate Model”, this is a consequence of the potential integration of the relevant service within the ICS-D, and the uncertainties of the relevant timeline.

2.4. Overview: data products P400, relevant to WP4

Data products in this group are related to WP4 activities, aiming at the implementation and optimization of the EPOS User Strategy to boost user engagement, through training and targeted communication. The specific data products are mostly connected to T4.2 and T4.3, which are the more practical ones, whereas 4.1 is more methodologically-oriented and is not supposed to produce data products other than deliverables and reports. Data products for this WP fall into three main categories:

- “P401 - Training materials”, in the form of Open Educational Resources (OER). This will include not only lessons, but all needed supporting materials for trainers and trainees, including trainers’ guide, scripts, exercises and solutions, additional resources, readme files etc. Self-paced materials (e.g. audiovisual) are also envisaged for this product type.
- “P402 – User feedback”, namely materials from User interviews, surveys and other interactions, that will be further analysed to provide recommendations on how to improve the EPOS Platform and other relevant outputs such as the training materials themselves. This product type includes interview recordings and/or transcripts (mainly in audiovisual and

textual formats), as well as structured data from surveys and user-experience sessions, etc. (mostly in tabular formats).

- Reusable code samples featuring automated scientific workflows, mainly for educational and demonstration purposes (Jupyter notebooks).

2.5. Overview: data products P600, relevant to WP6

This data product relates to activities within Task T6.3, which is developing an integrated back-office software tool capable of addressing different needs of the EPOS distributed infrastructure.

The tool will enable access to technical data of the EPOS services and complement it with contractual, financial and managerial information. Given the nature of the information managed within the tool its use is intended, at least for the part containing sensitive information, for the Executive Coordination Office alone. For this reason, a discussion about FAIRness of the data is not applicable so the only part of the data product being discussed in this document is the software itself, in Section 3.

3. FAIR data

3.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1. Findability: data products P100, relevant to WP1

Data types “P101 – Deliverables and publications” and “P104 – Communication material” will be uploaded to Zenodo, in the “EPOS Optimization and EvolutionN” community maintained by the data manager: https://zenodo.org/communities/epos_on

All data deposited to Zenodo will automatically receive a digital identifier (DOI). All deposited objects will be identified with a minimum set of metadata like title, description and list of authors. Furthermore, additional metadata will be used, wherever possible, to enrich the document description: for example, using tags (like “Project deliverable” or “Poster”), or describing links to other resources, or adding information about the event where the content was presented.

3.1.2. Findability: data products P200, relevant to WP2

As explained in chapter 2, data products in this group mainly involve the creation of metadata and the development of software, and the description thereof. All data products will have suitable PIDs: new community schemas and vocabularies possibly emerging from this activity will be published in Zenodo or at a similar vocabulary service (please also see the section on interoperability), while source code of Jupyter Notebooks demonstrating service usage and data analysis will be shared through public repositories of GitLab or GitHub.

Newly integrated services and ICS-D tools will be highly discoverable, through the use of the EPOS-DCAT-AP metadata schema and the EPOS vocabularies: actually, these will be improved and extended, also as a result of this activity, to improve findability. Moreover, metrics for findability from the FAIRsFAIR Data Object Assessment Metrics (v0.4, which are derived through GoFAIR from the RDA FAIR Data Maturity Framework) (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6461229>) will for instance be applied through assessment with the F-UJI tool (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6361400>). Findability on the basis of MQA indicators (<https://data.europa.eu/mqa/methodology?locale=en>) is assessed where the application of F-UJI is not feasible.

3.1.3. Findability: data products P300, relevant to WP3

Most data products are already associated with a persistent identifier, for example “P322 – Sea level sensors” ([10.14284/482](https://doi.org/10.14284/482)): when this is not the case, a suitable Persistent Identifier will be identified and associated.

Several datasets are available in GitHub under the respective repositories of the GEM community’s GitHub page <https://github.com/gem/>: (see following table): these repositories are assigned a DOI through the GEM community page in Zenodo <https://zenodo.org/communities/globalquakemodel>

Data Product	Repository
P341 – Global earthquake impact	https://github.com/gem/earthquake-scenarios
P342 – European exposure models	https://github.com/gem/global_exposure_model
P343 – Seismic vulnerability models	https://github.com/gem/global_vulnerability_model
P351 – Embodied Carbon Factors	https://github.com/gem/global_embodied_carbon_model
P352 – Replacement Embodied Carbon	
P353 – Average Annual Embodied Carbon	

Rich metadata will be provided, to maximise data findability: this will include the usage of specific keywords to simplify searching according to scientific topic, method, tools and geographic scope (e.g., “EEW” or “real-time seismology” for Earthquake Early Warning).

In general, metadata will adhere to standards in use within the relevant scientific communities. In some cases, additional metadata schemas will be evaluated, in order to improve the description of the data and maximise its exploitability in further data processing.

Specifically:

- “P311 – Alerts by EEW” will include, in standard TTL format, information about the seismic networks, the NFO responsible for the network, features of the used seismic records, organization responsible for the data; possibly, some information about the quality of data will also be included;
- “P341 – Global earthquake impact”, “P342 – European exposure models” and “P343 – Seismic vulnerability models” metadata will include geographic and temporal coverage, as well as information on data quality, licensing and access rights;

Metadata will be provided in a structured format, to facilitate harvesting and indexing by search engines and repositories.

3.1.4. Findability: data products P400, relevant to WP4

Data types “P401 – Training Materials” and “P403 – Automated workflows” will be uploaded to Zenodo, in the “EPOS Optimization and EvolutionN” community maintained by the data manager: https://zenodo.org/communities/epos_on

All data deposited to Zenodo will automatically receive a digital identifier (DOI). All deposited objects will be identified with a minimum set of metadata like title, description and list of authors. Furthermore, additional metadata will be used, wherever possible, to enrich the document description: for example using tags (like “Project deliverable” or “Poster”), or describing links to other resources, or adding information about the event where the content was presented. “P403 –

Automated workflows” will also be made available through the EPOS’ GitHub and directly linked from the EPOS Platform.

Regarding “P402 - User feedback” we need to draw a distinction between the individual responses to surveys, user interviews transcripts/ recording, User eXperience survey reports etc and the aggregated data and related analyses. The latter will also be the object of publication in Zenodo as for the other P400 data types. The former will be anonymised in order to protect the privacy of participants before further reuse. Survey/interview participants contact details will be kept for the duration of the project for further interactions, provided of course that the subjects have given their authorisation to be recontacted.

3.2. Making data accessible

Data stored in Zenodo is expected to be available for the next 20 years², at least.

Whenever deemed useful, for objects deposited in Zenodo, in order to simplify access to the most current information, a DOI will be reserved before uploading a new document, while the “collection DOI” (a special DOI guaranteed to point to the latest version of an object) will be referenced (for example, in the document’s first page): future updates of the object will be uploaded as new versions of the existing record. Referencing the “collection DOI” will ensure immediate access to the most recent version of an object, while also providing the possibility to access any intermediate existing version of it.

3.2.1. Accessibility: data products P100, relevant to WP1

All “P101 – Deliverables and publications” and “P104 – Communication material” data products are expected to be made openly available with no restriction and will be uploaded to Zenodo soon after being available in their final form. In particular, for “P101 – Deliverables and publications” this means right after submission to the Commission’s EU Funding and Tenders Portal, hence before the official approval by the Commission. This will be done in order to maximize their availability and chance to be reused: the approval status (“Submitted” or “Approved”) will be clearly marked in the document’s front page.

3.2.2. Accessibility: data products P200, relevant to WP2

According to the EPOS Data Policy, access to metadata (“P202 - Metadata for new/extended communities”) and service descriptions (“P201 - Service description”) will always be free and available at any time, even when the underlying data (managed by the Service Provider) may be restricted or embargoed. As for “P203 - Software prototypes”, this will be software developed within EPOS and hence, according to the EPOS Data Policy, will be made openly available. Still, some limited embargo time on the actual code may apply, but the metadata in such cases will be openly accessible. As such, software code is on a par with its data counterpart.

²<https://about.zenodo.org/policies/>

3.2.3. Accessibility: data products P300, relevant to WP3

Data products will be deposited in trusted repositories, and assigned an identifier, when one is not already present. Continuous data will likely not be deposited real-time, but on set intervals.

Generally speaking, data will be made openly available, without an embargo period. Access to the data will be open under the CC-BY license, while metadata will be covered by CC0 license: metadata will be supplemented by access instructions.

Some exceptions to the above are foreseen for data containing sensitive information, as is the case for:

- “P311 – Alerts by EEW”: the data will be accessible via the CREW platform, but it is being discussed whether to make periodic backups available via Zenodo;
- “P321 – Forecast Points”: will be made available to NEAM TSPs, although details about access level are still under discussion; the possibility of an embargo period will also be discussed within NEAMTWS TSPs; these latter will also identify a set of users to be granted individual access credentials;
- “P342 – European exposure models” will be openly available at administrative Level³ 1, through the dedicated GitHub repository; higher resolution models will be provided upon request and subject to a custom licensing agreement and identity verification, following the established practice used for other GEM models;
- “P351 – Embodied Carbon Factors”, “P352 – Replacement Embodied Carbon”, “P353 – Average Annual Embodied Carbon” will be openly available at administrative Level⁴ 1, through the dedicated GitHub repository; higher resolution models will be provided upon request and subject to a custom licensing agreement and identity verification, following the established practice used for other GEM models; interactive web services will be accessible via the EPOS Built Environmental Data service at <https://builtenvdata.eu/>

3.2.4. Accessibility: data products P400, relevant to WP4

Data types “P401 – Training Materials” and “P403 – Automated workflows” and the aggregated information on user feedback (i.e. the public part of P402) are expected to be made openly available with no restriction and will be uploaded to Zenodo soon after being available in their final form. Accessibility to the source data from P402 will be restricted and respect the authorisation provided by participants.

³ According to the definition within the “EPOS Data Policy” (<https://www.epos-eu.org/data-policy-2018>): Level 1 refers to “data products coming from (nearly) automated procedures”

⁴ See previous note

3.3. Making data interoperable

3.3.1. Interoperability: data products P100, relevant to WP1

Given the expected kind of data falling in categories “P101 – Deliverables and publications” and “P104 – Communication material”, we believe the metadata description provided within Zenodo will be detailed enough to cater for interoperability. However, should the metadata be deemed insufficient to such purpose, the data object will be supplemented with a README file.

3.3.2. Interoperability: data products P200, relevant to WP2

All data products in this category pertain to the realization of services within the EPOS Platform: for this reason, the goal of interoperability will be achieved by adhering to the standards defined at EPOS community level (TCSs) as well as to the service integration process defined for the EPOS Platform. As such, levels of interoperability will be aligned with ongoing developments in the applicable fields of research, thereby taking into account the cross-disciplinary requirements from the EPOS Platform perspective.

Vocabulary management is beyond the scope of these data products and of the WP2 workpackage of EPOS ON. However, if during the integration phase new community schemas and/or vocabularies will be identified, these will be duly described, published to Zenodo or similar service, and referenced.

3.3.3. Interoperability: data products P300, relevant to WP3

Since these data products will be developed in the context of EPOS ON and the EPOS ERIC, interoperability will be catered for “by design”: this includes adhering to existing procedures and, when needed, making vocabularies and specific ontologies available, to guarantee the use and the re-use of the services.

Data and metadata formats conform to the standards in use in the relevant research communities.

Whenever useful in order to complement the informative content of the data, additional data will be adequately referenced.

Some data products introduce a terminology which is rather new in the relevant research fields. Such cases are discussed below:

- “P353 - Average Annual Embodied Carbon” is a newly created term within the seismic risk and environmental impact assessment research fields. This terminology is supported by a publication currently under review (<https://www.researchsquare.com/article/rs-5283610/v1>). Any additional terms that emerge during the course of this work will be thoroughly documented and explained on the BED website. Where needed, mappings to more widely used ontologies and vocabularies will be openly described.

3.4. Increase data re-use

3.4.1. Re-usability: data products P100, relevant to WP1

The combined use of metadata and, whenever useful, README files, will provide all information needed to make our data reusable, for example details about data generation and collection as well as about licenses.

“P101 – Deliverables and publications” and “P104 – Communication material” data will be made available as per the quality assurance procedures defined by the project and described in deliverable “D1.1 – Management and Quality Control Plan” (<https://zenodo.org/records/14222722>).

We will use file formats suited for data re-use and long-term preservation (e.g., by including fonts within docx files, or by using PDF/A format).

3.4.2. Re-usability: data products P200, relevant to WP2

Newly integrated services and new software tools will follow the EPOS integration policies, in particular for all matters related to proper documentation (also machine-readable), information about creators and maintainers, licensing, as well as aspects related to quality assurance during development. The EPOS policies themselves are on a par with EU guidelines for open science with respect to the reuse of digital research assets.

3.4.3. Re-usability: data products P300, relevant to WP3

In order to guarantee data and services re-use, suitable documentation will be provided and kept up-to-date, in the form of readme files, webpages, or other suitable documentation types.

Data which does not contain sensitive information will be made freely available under the terms of the Creative Commons CC-BY-4.0 license.

Any EPOS ON outcome is meant to be explicitly reused within the EPOS ERIC. This is also the case for the data produced, which is aimed to be used within the EPOS Platform after the end of the project: in addition, some data products may be used also by third parties (Civil Protection, Research Institutes, Universities).

Data provenance (original sources, collection methods and post-processing steps) will be documented according to appropriate standards.

As for quality assurance (data collection methods, data validation, consistency checks, guidelines, version control,...), data products in this category will follow the common practice within the relevant EPOS TCS service, for example:

- “P321 – Global Acoustic Meteotsunami” and “P322 – Global earthquake impact” will follow the process defined by the EPOS TCS-TSU and described at <https://tsunamidata.org/organization/data-quality-assurance> ;

3.4.4. Re-usability: data products P400, relevant to WP4

The combined use of metadata and, whenever useful, README files, will provide all information needed to make our data reusable, for example details about data generation and collection as well as about licenses.

“P401 – Training Materials” in particular will be prepared following a FAIR-by-Design methodology (cfr for example the one suggested⁵ by the Skills4EOSC Project). In a nutshell, this means Open Formats, Open licenses and instructions for trainers and trainees on how to reuse and update the materials, typically in the form of documentation attached or linked and cross-referencing to the main file, and made available as OERs to maximise reuse. Special attention will be paid to using file formats suited for data re-use and long-term preservation (e.g., by including fonts within docx files, or by using PDF/A format, and/or providing content separated from the format e.g. markdown or text files when appropriate). “P403 – Automated workflows” will be made available with OS licenses and provided with documentation to facilitate reuse.

⁵ <https://www.skills4eosoc.eu/resources/fair-by-design-methodology>

4. Other research outputs

4.1. Data products P100, relevant to WP1

Data products “P102 – Project management documents”, “P103 – Project management workspace” and “P105 – Lists of contacts” more directly relate to the execution of the EPOS ON project. Note that, in the following, we will refer to “project lifetime” to mean the timespan covering through the “full” project completion, namely the timespan needed to fulfil obligations contained in the Grant Agreement (5 years after project completion).

From the point of view of data access, part of the data will be accessible project-wise, while access to some other data (e.g., administrative information) will need to be restricted (e.g., administrative contacts and beneficiaries representatives).

From the point of view of data retention, part of the data is more strictly connected to project execution and hence will need to be accessible through the project’s lifetime, while some other data will directly contribute to the consolidation of the RI and thus needs to outlive the EPOS ON project.

The software tools in use within the EPOS ON project are, at time of writing, the following:

- Confluence: is the project workspace developed by Atlassian. EPOS ON has access to an instance in the Atlassian cloud (epos-on.atlassian.net). Confluence will be used to store data such as meeting minutes or tasks lists, manage task assignment and execution, and store some documents of general interest to project participants. We are not considering implementing access control on this platform, meaning that any Confluence user will have full visibility of all Confluence “spaces” dedicated to the EPOS ON project. The Confluence instance dedicated to EPOS ON is GDPR-compliant, and the relevant data is configured to be stored in AWS cloud regions in Europe.
 - Confluence will be used for material which needs to be available to any project participant, for the duration of the EPOS ON project
- Google drive: is the cloud-based storage service developed by Google, which includes software for real-time collaboration on Office documents.
 - Google drive will be used for material which needs to be accessible to project participants also after the closure of the EPOS ON project
- Intranet: refers to an instance of “Nextcloud hub” installed on EPOS ERIC’s own resources, and directly managed by EPOS ERIC staff. It provides management of mailing lists and cloud repositories, implements access controls and is fully GDPR compliant.
 - Intranet will be used, during and after the EPOS ON project, for material which needs to be restricted to specific individuals and/or profiles

4.2. Data products P200 (WP2), P300 (WP3), P600 (WP6)

All software developed in the context of WP2, WP3 and WP6 work packages will be managed as described below.

During the period of development, the software source code will be stored on private servers. All software written in the course of this work will normally be open source and be made available to other researchers, in accordance with EPOS recommendations: at time of writing, we are not aware of cases where internal policies of the affected communities impose any additional constraints. No special-purpose software or hardware will be required for access. Upon project completion the source code will be moved from private servers to a public site, which is a stable, readily available, and well-maintained repository for open-source information. Candidate sites are GitLab and GitHub; the choice will be finalized during the project; in any case the hosting site will contain wiki pages explaining how to use the software and how to contribute to the open source code.

5. Allocation of resources

There is no cost associated with making data FAIR as this is mandated by default, according to the “EPOS Digital Assets Management Policy”⁶.

The data manager, staff personnel at EPOS ERIC, is responsible for the overall data management of the EPOS ON project, while WP leaders are responsible for ensuring quality control activities of the datasets pertaining to their respective WP. Finally, researchers are responsible for routine supervision of the dataset development.

⁶ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14780661>

6. Data security

All repositories used to store data objects of the EPOS ON project implement measures for data security (confidentiality, integrity, availability). Only for the case of “Intranet”, though, these measures are directly under control (and visibility) of EPOS ERIC, while for other repositories we rely on the relevant information on policies and terms of reference.

In all cases where personal data will need to be collected and processed, barring cases of “legitimate interest”, we will gain an informed consent: the relevant information will be stored in EPOS ERIC “Intranet” space.

The EPOS Platform is not storing any research data, as it is intended as a tool to access existing data collected, curated and provided by the relevant scientific communities. Likewise, the EPOS ON project will not directly be involved in the storage of research data. This will happen at the level of the research communities, following the EPOS best practices: for example, data of Level⁷ 1 and above will be stored in multiple copies, possibly at geographically distant sites, and subject to regular backup as well as restore verification.

As for software services, these are configured to ensure resiliency against possible failures.

⁷ Refer to definitions within the “EPOS Data Policy” (<https://www.epos-eu.org/data-policy-2018>), classifying data from Level 0 (raw data) to Level 3 (integrated data products resulting from complex analysis)

7. Ethics

Personal data, mostly contained in P100 and P400 data products, will be treated according to the GDPR prescriptions.

No other data product seems to involve, at time of writing, any ethical issue. Should any concern arise, it will be discussed within the EPOS ON Task *“T3.3 - Methodology for an ethical label applicable to services”* and this section will be duly updated.

8. Other issues

The data products discussed in this document will not make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management, with the exceptions of:

- P300: The possibility to exploit the INGV Open Data Portal <https://data.ingv.it/> to store metadata and to obtain a digital object identifier (DOI) will be evaluated;
- “P361 - Rapid Earthquake Infographic”: the design of the prototype application will be submitted to the ethics commission of ETH Zurich, and all data will be handled in accordance with the Swiss Data Protection Law;
- “P371 – ETAS models”: to ensure compliance with best practices, procedures for data management such as [ETH Zurich’s guidelines](#)⁸ will be followed

⁸ <https://rechtssammlung.sp.ethz.ch/Dokumente/414.2en.pdf>